

INFLUENCE OF CNT BUCKYPAPER ON THE INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH OF LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, carbon nanotube (CNT) buckypapers (BPs) were prepared and introduced to improve the interlaminar shear strength of a composite laminate. The BPs were directly incorporated into the middle interface of the laminates. End-notch flexure (ENF) and short beam shear (SBS) tests were conducted to examine the influence of the obtained BPs on mode II interlaminar fracture toughness and interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of the laminates. Results have shown the porous CNT BPs would enhance the mode II fracture toughness and ILSS up to 80% and 30%, respectively. Improved interfacial bonding was obtained with the CNT BPs interleaves.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been the focal point of many investigations for use as reinforcements of polymeric nanocomposites since the CNTs/epoxy composites were first fabricated and investigated by Ajayan et al. in 1994 [1]. Due to their high surface-to-volume ratio, even at a low concentration (usually less than 4 wt. %), CNTs make the polymer solution very viscous, which leads to the undesired dispersion and distribution of CNTs in polymeric nanocomposites [2-6]. These unavoidable problems make the achieved properties of the nanocomposites much lower than expected. One promising way to solve the above problems is to macroscopically assemble CNTs into the thin buckypaper (also called sheet, mat, or web) and then to infiltrate the buckypaper with polymer matrix to form reinforced composites [5]. The CNT buckypaper is a macroscopic, paper-like material composed of continuous entangled CNTs networks with a highly porous structure, in which, the CNTs are free-standing in random direction [5, 6]. The paper-like nanomaterial can be used for a wide range of applications, such as mechanical reinforcing and functional device fields.

Delamination is one of the primary damage patterns when the laminated composite structures are subjected to external transverse loads. The occurrence of delamination damage greatly reduces the stiffness and strength of a structure, and often leads to a serious failure during service [7]. A lot of researches have already been carried out to study the toughening methods for the delamination resistance, such as matrix modification or interleaving [8-10]. CNT porous BPs have been considered as one of the most promising interleaves due to its superior mechanical properties. But to date, only limited reports about CNT BPs acted as secondary reinforcing materials especially used as interleaves or interlayers can be found from the published literatures.

The aim of this study is to investigate the influence of the CNT buckypapers (BPs) prepared by positive pressure filtration method on the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness and interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of a composite laminate. The obtained porous webs were used to in situ toughen the interlaminar properties of a carbon fibre (CF)/epoxy laminate.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Multi-walled CNTs (8~15 nm in diameter and 5~15 μm in length) used in this study were purchased from Chengdu Organic Chemicals Co. The CNTs were obtained as suspension with equal weight ratio of carboxylated CNTs (1.85 wt. % of Carboxyl ratio). T700/epoxy prepregs (made in Guangwei Group) with an average thickness 0.20 mm were employed to fabricate the composite laminates.

The CNTs suspension was filtrated through a membrane with a pore size of $0.8\ \mu\text{m}$ under an aid of positive pressure ($0.1\sim 0.3\ \text{MPa}$). The obtained BPs were then immersed with nitric acid for 5 min to remove surfactant. Then, the BPs were washed with distilled water to remove impurities and acid, and were directly dried as as-prepared BPs. The final square BP was shown in Fig. 1a, with a thickness about $18\sim 23\ \mu\text{m}$ and a length of 200 mm.

Figure 1: The obtained BP (a) and the microstructure of the BP zoomed in (a).

Two panels, 16 layers of the T700/epoxy prepregs were arranged unidirectionally ($[0]_{16}$), were prepared and investigated. The first laminate was a base laminate. The second plate was incorporated with BP on the middle interface. After stacking the plies for the intended laminates, the plates were vacuum bagged and put into an autoclave. The laminates were heated up to $120\ ^\circ\text{C}$ at a rate of $1\ ^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, and were hold at $120\ ^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h. Afterwards, the laminates were cooled down to room temperature for further characterization. During the isothermal time, the applied outer pressure is $0.58\ \text{MPa}$.

The final morphology of the BP was observed with a SEM machine (Philips XL 30 ESEM instrument). Following references [11,12], the length of the ENF specimens was selected as 200 mm, with a width of 25 mm and a pre-crack length of 50 mm (see in Fig.2). The thickness of cured laminates was between 2.98 and 3.04 mm. Three to five specimens were cut from each laminate. While, the ILSS specimens were cut according to ASTM D2344 standard. The ENF tests were conducted on a universal testing machine (Model CSS-44020, Changchun Institute of Testing Machine). The crosshead speed for loading the specimens was $2\ \text{mm}/\text{min}$ for the tests. Fractured side-sections and fractured surfaces of some typical specimens after the testing were characterized using an XL 30 ESEM machine.

Figure 2: The mode II interlaminar fracture toughness testing specimen and dimensions.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure of the BP

Fig. 1b showed SEM images of the BPs. It clearly showed that the CNTs were randomly standing-free on the BP with uniform distribution. The CNT BP is porous with relatively homogeneous open pores, showing porous structure from the view point of micro-morphology.

3.2 Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness

Typical load vs displacement curve which was close to the average for each laminate was chosen out and given in Fig. 3a. By incorporating the CNT interleaves, the fractured loads were improved, from 900 to 1000 N. The calculated mode II critical strain energy release rates, G_{IIc} , for laminates with and without CNT BP were presented in Fig. 3b. The CNT BP has significant toughening effect on the G_{IIc} , up to 73% for the reinforced laminate.

Side-edge views of the fractured ENF specimens were presented in Figs. 3 and 4. The crack in the neat laminate (Fig. 4a) propagated along a relatively straight path without deflection, indicating that there was a low delamination resistance. Debonding between the CFs and resin was significant in the whole interlaminar zone, suggesting crack propagation along CFs/resin interface in a brittle manner which was confirmed by a high magnification (Fig. 4b). The cracks in the reinforced laminate propagated in a zig-zag pattern, which meant delamination resistances were larger (shown in Fig.5a). Higher magnified views in Fig. 5b showed that the cracks mainly propagated within the CNT BP/resin interlayer, and the debonding of CFs/resin interface is not obviously seen.

Moreover, the fracture surfaces of the laminates with and without CNT BP were evaluated as shown in Fig. 6. For the neat laminate, the interfacial debonding of CFs/resin and brittle rupture of resin were observed (Fig. 6a), while improved deform of resin and interfacial bonding between CFs/resin were obtained in the interleaved laminates (Fig. 6b). In the region far-off the initiation of crack, it could be seen that more resin were covered on the surfaces of CFs for the interleaved laminates, and the fracture surfaces of resin were rougher and looked like ripples and dimples (Fig.6b).

Figure 3: Load-displacement curves (a) and mode II critical strain energy release rate (b).

Figure 4: Mode II fractured side-sections of laminate without CNT BP, (a) and (b) denoted various magnifications.

Figure 5: Mode II fractured side-sections of laminate with CNT BP, (a) and (b) denoted various magnifications.

Figure 6: Mode II fractured surfaces of laminates, (a) and (b) denoted neat and reinforced laminates, respectively

3.3 ILSS

The ILSS of the laminates with and without CNT BP interleave were shown in Fig. 7. Results have suggested that the ILSS was improved by 29% of the interleaved laminate compared with that of the neat laminate. The ILSS is dominated by the resin matrix, which has been toughened and strengthened by the CNTs. Thus, the enhancement on the ILSS is more obvious. Once more, the benefits of the used CTN webs are verified.

Figure 7: Interlaminar shear strength of the plates with and without CNT BP

The fractured surfaces of the laminates with and without CNT BP were given in Fig.8. Fracture of resin, interfacial debonding of carbon fibers and epoxy resin were the main fracture characterizations. It was obvious that the fractured resins were shown brittle rupture. While, the BP reinforced laminate

mainly showed fracture of resin, improved interfacial bonding were obtained. It also can be seen that the fractured resins were rough, there were enwrapped with a thin layer of resin on the carbon fibers surfaces.

It should be noted that previous studies have shown CNT pull-out and crack bridging are the major toughening mechanisms of the hybrid composites. Actually, easy pull-out of CNTs from resin matrix means weaker interfacial bonding between CNTs and resin. In this study, crack bridging was observed, but the pull-out phenomenon was unremarkable. On the other hand, CNTs dots on the fracture surfaces are dominant views, suggesting good interfacial bonding between CNTs and resin matrix which was due to the well functionalized chemical groups and well operations.

Figure 8: Fractured surfaces of the plates with and without CNT BP, (a) neat plate and (b) reinforced plate

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, CNT buckypaper were obtained. The interface improved by the CNT buckypaper contributes to the interlaminar fracture toughness of the composite laminate. The G_{IIC} is improved by 73% for the laminates interleaved with CNT buckypaper compared with that of the neat laminate. Similarly, increase in ILSS rate up to 29% was also obtained. The breakage of CFs and CNTs as well as the resin deformation preceding fracture are concluded as the primary toughening mechanisms. Usually, toughening and strengthening are conflictive with each other, while the present study demonstrates that the proposed porous webs not only benefit the toughness of the laminates but also have positive effect on the strength.

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